

THE EFFECT OF COMPENSATION AND THE WORK ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEE LOYALTY WITH EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE

Raden Assyifa Nuraini¹, Lia Amalia²

Universitas Esa Unggul

Email: rdnassyifanuraini@gmail.com¹, lia.amalia@esaunggul.ac.id²

Abstrak – Teknologi dan sumber daya manusia adalah dua komponen yang sangat penting dalam bisnis makanan cepat saji, yang merupakan sektor padat karya. Sektor makanan cepat saji harus memahami perilaku pekerjanya karena sumber daya manusia ini, membuat penelitian ini menjadi penting. Sektor makanan cepat saji PT Rekso Nasional Food mempekerjakan 252 responden staf untuk penelitian ini, yang dilakukan dengan menggunakan kuesioner yang didistribusikan dan Analisis Model Persamaan Struktural (SEM). Temuan penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa kebahagiaan kerja dipengaruhi secara positif oleh gaji dan tempat kerja. Sebaliknya, loyalitas tidak dipengaruhi secara positif oleh uang. Pekerja PT Rekso Nasional Food lebih loyal karena lingkungan kerjanya. Pengaruh lingkungan kerja yang baik terhadap loyalitas karyawan PT Rekso Nasional Food tidak dapat dimediasi oleh kebahagiaan karyawan. konsekuensi bagi restoran McDonald's untuk memikirkan gaji, tempat kerja, dan loyalitas agar dapat meningkatkan keterlibatan karyawan dan berhasil memenuhi tujuan perusahaan

Kata Kunci: Kompensasi, Lingkungan Kerja, Kepuasan, Loyalitas

Abstract – *Technology and human resources are two highly essential components in the fast-food business, which is a labor-intensive sector. The fast-food sector must understand the behavior of its workers due to these human resources, making this study crucial. PT Rekso Nasional Food's fast-food sector employed 252 staff respondents for the research, which was carried out utilizing a distributed questionnaire and a Structural Equation Model (SEM) Analysis. The findings of this research demonstrate that job happiness is positively impacted by pay and the workplace. In contrast, loyalty is not positively impacted by money. The PT Rekso Nasional Food workers are more loyal as a result of their work environment. The favorable impact of the work environment on the loyalty of the employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food cannot be mediated by employee happiness. consequences for McDonald's restaurants to think about pay, the workplace, and loyalty in order to be able to enhance employee engagement and successfully meet company objectives.*

Keywords: *Compensation, Work Environment, Satisfaction, Loyalty*

INTRODUCTION

Employees play a significant part in the key elements that might affect a company's success in the food and beverage business. According to Parveen (2019), the need for employees is to create a relationship between management and employees, in terms of employee performance and employee loyalty. Realizing the importance of human resource relationships for the survival and progress of the company, the company must have measures to encourage employees optimally and be able to meet the key performance index that has been set (Cooper et al. , 2019) . In addition, the current economic challenges require a good process of transformation of human resources (Rosario Núñez et al., 2020). So, it is necessary for employees who have high loyalty to the company. Loyal employees are an important asset for the business as it ensures the success of the business (Esmaeilpour and Ranjbar, 2018). There are several factors that affect employee loyalty, namely compensation and work environment.

Compensation is one of the factors that can affect employee satisfaction and performance. Because organizations must provide adequate compensation and benefits to employees in accordance with the workload given to them (Tam and Nguyet, 2021). Compensation is an impetus to improve employee satisfaction and performance. Compensation is a factor that affects employees so that the company can provide fair compensation so that employee satisfaction increases and is loyal to the company (Reny et al., 2021). Compensation can also be given in the form of recognition or appreciation of the results of employee work and can increase work attachment to the company (Robianto, Masdupi, and Syahrizal, 2020). Other benefits can be health insurance and paid or non-financial leave, flexible working arrangements and welfare programs to improve employee morale, satisfaction, and commitment (Patiar and Wang, 2020). A fair form of compensation can ultimately provide increased loyalty to employees (Ali, 2020).

Employee work environment is able to stimulate and recognize the creative capacity of employees (Ramos, Figueiredo, and Pereira-Guizzo, 2018). A positive work environment also occurs when the employee has a good relationship with colleagues because they can work in harmony with them to complete the work given to him (Samat et al. , 2020) . According to Zufri et al. (2022) One of them is environmental comfort, employee loyalty can be triggered by a comfortable work environment, in which workers feel comfortable and not disturbed by their work environment. A comfortable work environment, which includes physical aspects such as lighting, temperature, color, and layout, as well as non-physical aspects such as the relationship between colleagues and superiors, makes employees feel at home, and this comfort makes employees not consider looking for another job (Zufri et al. , 2022) .

Employee satisfaction is an important issue in relation to generating employee loyalty. Employee satisfaction and loyalty provide similarities and also significant differences in the context of the organizational environment (Mohd Said et al. , 2020). Job satisfaction is an important thing that can build organizational psychology so that it will affect employee behavior (Che et al., 2019). Employees believe that working for this company is their best option. Loyalty cannot be expected without reciprocity. To expect a high level of loyalty from employees, then the company must show the same, or even higher, the level of its loyalty to them. (Wilson et al. , 2021). So employees need to get satisfaction which ultimately has an impact on high loyalty to the company.

Based on the results of research conducted by previous researchers related to compensation to employee satisfaction such as research conducted by Ashraf (2020); Butt et al. (2020); Samat et al. (2020); Wulandari et al. (2021); Kholis et al. , (2022). Meanwhile, research related to the Work Environment on employee satisfaction such as research conducted by Anasi (2020); Hauret and Williams (2020); Hur (2020); Pawirosumarto et al. (2017). For research related to compensation for employee loyalty such as research conducted by Budiyo et al. (2022); Samat et al. (2020); Wulandari et al. (2021); Zufri et al., (2022). Finally, research

related to the Work Environment on employee loyalty such as research conducted by Aboobaker et al. (2021); Ramadhanty et al. (2020); Samat et al. (2020); Susita et al. (2020); Zufri et al. (2022).

The research produced conflicting findings, although the previous study employed employee responses from the manufacturing, banking, and education industries, while this study focused on the fast-food sector. In the previous survey, respondents with bachelor's degrees were utilized; in this study, respondents with degrees ranging from high school to master's were used. In contrast to the previous research, which did not incorporate all of the factors into one thorough analysis, this study did so while also included the intermediary variable of employee satisfaction. With the research period beginning in 2022, this study will also examine the effects of pay and the workplace on the happiness and loyalty of fast-food workers in Indonesia.

According to the findings of the aforementioned description, the aim of this research is to investigate and evaluate the impact that the link between pay and work environment has on employee loyalty, using satisfaction as a mediator variable. This research also serves as an assessment and corrective tool for fast food industry management, enabling them to understand how pay and the workplace environment affect employee loyalty while using satisfaction as a company-wide mediating variable. While this is going on, other parties involved in the study may utilize it as a resource, do analyses, and learn how to gauge the impact of these factors so that it can be very beneficial to society.

RESEARCH METHODS

Measurement

This study used descriptive quantitative research using compensation variables according to Ahmat et al. (2019) with 4 dimensions and 4 indicators, while the work environment variable according to Gordon (2000); Pawirosumarto et al. (2017) with 3 Dimensions and 3 indicators. Furthermore, the satisfaction variable according to (Smith, 1969); (Pawirosumarto et al. , 2017) with 5 dimensions and 10 indicators, lastly loyalty according to López-Jáuregui et al. (2019) ; Aristana et al. (2022) with 8 dimensions and 8 indicators. In this measurement the researcher will disseminate a questionnaire using a linkert scale of 1-5 where the score of 1 is Strongly disagree, the score is 2 Disagree, the score is 3 neutral and the score is 4 agrees and the score 5 strongly agrees.

Population, Sample, and Research Location

The population in this study was taken from all employees who worked at PT Rekso Nasional Food, this company was in charge of the Mc Donald's Franchise in Indonesia. The total number of Mc Donald's Franchise employees in Indonesia totals more than 10,000 people spread throughout Indonesia. The respondents in this study were employees who worked at PT Rekso Nasional Food master Franchise Corporation Mc Donald's in Indonesia with a total of 252 people in 2022. This purposive sampling technique is determined by a minimum high school education, a position as a crew, and a working period of more than 1 year, and the work location is in the Jabodetabek area. The reason for using this purposive sampling technique is because it is suitable for use in quantitative research or research that does not make generalizations.

Data Analysis Methods

After all the results of the questionnaire are collected by the researcher, then a validity test will be carried out using 30 questionnaire samples, if the calculated t value is greater than the significant value of the > 0.255 then the validity of the questionnaire is valid. And if the calculated value of t count is greater than the significant value of > 0.6 then rites electability is reliable. All data will be analyzed using Structural Equation Models (SEM) where SEM is a multivariate statistical technique that combines all aspects of factor analysis, path analysis and

regression so that the results of the analysis become more complete (Hair et al., 2018) . One of the other advantages of the Structural Equation Model (SEM) is the ability to create construct models as latent variables or variables that are not measured directly, but are estimated in the model of the variables that are measured and that are assumed to have a relationship with these variables latent variables. Furthermore, for data processing, it is processed using statistical software.

RESULT

Research Results

This study used Lisrel (Linear Structural Relationship) 8.8 software to find out and find out about the relationship of two variables, namely the variables of compensation, work environment, satisfaction and loyalty to PT Rekso Nasional Food as an outlet of PT Rekso Nasional Food in Indonesia.

Statistical Descriptive Test

Conducting a statistical descriptive test with up to 252 respondents is important to have a general idea of the traits of workers in the environment of PT Rekso Nasional Food that will be investigated. The gender, age, employment, education, and length of service of the respondents in this research were noted in the delivery of the data. The basic data utilized in this research were derived from questionnaires that were separated into 25 indicators or statements, each of which represented 4 latent variables. Following are the responses' specifics:

Table 1. Descriptive Respondents

STATUS	CRITERION	SUM	%
GENDER	Man	151	60%
	Woman	101	40%
AGE	☐ 22-26 years old	28	11%
	☐ 27 -31 years old	151	60%
	☐ 32- 36 years old	68	27%
	☐ 36-40 years old	3	1%
	☐ 41 - 45 years old	2	1%
	☐ > 45 years old	0	0%
EDUCATION	☐ High School -SMK	180	71%
	☐ D3	52	21%
	☐ S1	18	7%
	☐ S2	2	1%
EMPLOYEE STATUS	Fulltime ☐	75	30%
	☐ PKWT	6	2%
	Internship ☐	171	68%
LENGTH OF WORK	☐ 1-2 years	29	11%
	☐ 3-5 years	190	75%
	☐ 6-10 years	28	11%
	☐ More than 10 years	5	2%

Validity Test And Reliability Of Measurement Model Liabilities

By examining the value of the loading factor, validity tests are conducted to determine the degree of correctness of the data. The standardized loading factor of each variable indicator was determined from the output of Lisrel and accepted for use in this investigation. Perform a reliability test whether the data are reliable. To determine the degree of its dependability, test it. All variables may be deemed trustworthy based on the processed result since they all have Cronbach Alpha values greater than 0.6. The following step, which includes confirmatory factor analysis, will be continued with the declaration of valid and reliable variables in this research.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Each indicator and latent variable in this research will now undergo validity and reliability testing. A test called a validity test seeks to establish if an indicator can accurately measure a hidden variable. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, which has a minimum threshold of 0.5, is evaluated as the validity test in this research. In contrast, Composite Reliability, which has a minimum value of 0.6, is used in the reliability test. The standardized loading factor of compensation has a value over 0.6 based on Lisrel's output. This demonstrates the validity and statistical significance of the four indications in the compensation variable. The work environment's standardized loading factor is more than 0.6. This indicates that none of the three indicators for the work environment variable should be removed since they are all legitimate and statistically significant. The satisfaction standard loading factor is more than 0.6. This indicates that none of the 10 indicators for the satisfaction measure should be removed since they are all legitimate and statistically significant. Loyalty's standardized loading factor is more than 0.6. This suggests that none of the 8 indications for the loyalty variable should be removed since they are all legitimate and statistically significant.

Goodness Of Fit

Measurements are made using a variety of indices to determine if a model may be deemed practical. Each index has a minimum measurement that must be met on its own in order to be considered viable; however, this does not imply that the model is in fact fit. On the other hand, a very poor index does not always mean that the model cannot be implemented. The degree of agreement between the data and the model is evaluated during the model fit testing step (Goodness of Fit). I am aware that 12 model conformance measurements have been deemed to be satisfactory. Nine criteria are found to have a good fit based on the results of the match test, which allows the model to proceed for structural testing since it has been found to be appropriate. While the three requirements are deemed to be unfit.

Coefficient Of Determination (R-Square)

The R-Square value may be used to determine the coefficient of determination. The independent variable's ability to explain the dependent variable is improved with a greater value. How well the dependent variable is represented by the change of independent variables in the research model is shown by the coefficient of determination, or R-square. As can be observed, the R-square value for satisfaction is 0.94, meaning that the variables of variation, remuneration, and work environment account for 94% of the satisfaction variable. While changes in other factors account for the remaining 6%. In contrast, the R-square for loyalty is 0.91, indicating that differences in remuneration, work environment, and satisfaction account for 91% of this variable. While changes in other factors account for the remaining 9%.

Structural Model Fit Test

Figure 2 Structural Pathway Model (Standardized Solution)

Test The Direct Effect Hypothesis

The test results of each hypothesis obtained the t-value as follows:

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Coefficient	T-value	Result
H1: Compensation has a positive effect on Employee Satisfaction.	0,11	2,27	Data supports hypotheses
H2: The Work Environment has a positive effect on Employee Satisfaction.	0,11	6,52	Data supports hypotheses
H3: Compensation positively affects Loyalty	0,23	1.74	The data does not support the hypothesis
H4: Work Environment positively affects Loyalty	0.20	5,60	Data supports hypotheses
H5: Satisfaction negatively affects Loyalty	0,15	-2,82	The data does not support the hypothesis

Based on the table above, the results of testing the hypothesis were obtained, namely; first, compensation for employee satisfaction there is a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.11 with a t-stat value of 2.27 (>1.97). Thus, hypothesis 1 can be accepted. Second, the work environment to employee satisfaction has a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.11 and has a significant effect with a t-stat value of 6.52 (>1.97). Thus, then Hypothesis 2 is accepted. Third, compensation for employee loyalty has a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.23 and with a t-stat value of 1.74 (<1.97). Thus, then hypothesis 3 rejected. Fourth, the environment of work and loyalty there is a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.20 with a t-stat value of 5.60 (>1.97). Thus, hypothesis 4 is acceptable and there is a significant influence between the environment and loyalty. Fifth, satisfaction and loyalty there is a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.15 with a t-stat value of -2.82 (<1.97). Thus, hypothesis 5 can be accepted and but there is a significant negative influence between satisfaction and loyalty.

Test The Indirect Effect Hypothesis

Table 5. Test the Indirect Effect Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Coefficient	T-value	Result
H6: Compensation Positively Affects Loyalty Mediated Satisfaction	0,05	-1.99	The data does not support the hypothesis
H7: Work Environment Negatively Affects Loyalty In Satisfaction Mediation	0.13	-2.42	The data does not support the hypothesis

Fifth, with a coefficient value of 0.05 and a t-statistic value of -1.99 (>1.97), there is no positive link between pay for loyalty and satisfaction. As a result, hypothesis 6 may be disproved and there is no intermediary between loyalty and pleasure. With a coefficient value of 0.13 and a value of t-stat-2.42 (>1.97), the six indicates that there is a positive association between the work environment and loyalty through mediating satisfaction. As a result, Hypothesis 7 can be disproved and there is no discernible impact.

DISCUSSION

The Effect Of Compensation On Employee Satisfaction

In the results of the first hypothesis test (H1) it was found that compensation had a positive effect on employee satisfaction of PT Rekso Nasional Food. This result indicates that compensation at PT Rekso Nasional Food perceived by employees as measured based on indicators of salary, incentives, benefits and facilities has proven to be able to increase employee job satisfaction, by measuring based on the indicators of the job itself, salary, job

promotion, supervision, co-workers. The results of this study are in accordance with research that has been carried out by several previous studies, namely Ashraf (2020); Butt et al. (2020); Samat et al. (2020); Wulandari et al. (2021); Kholis et al. (2022) which explains in his research that compensation has a positive effect on employee satisfaction. The provision of salary is a determinant of compensation for employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food. This can be used as an encouragement to work is to get a salary and at PT Rekso Nasional Food in a salary of more than the minimum wage (UMK) so as to make employees interested in joining PT Rekso Nasional Food. Compensation is often regarded as one of the important factors in improving employee satisfaction and is seen as key in improving employee well-being.

The Effect Of The Environment On Employee Satisfaction

In the results of the second hypothesis test (H2) it was found that the work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction, the work environment is a place where employees carry out activities every day. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and allows employees to be able to work optimally. The results of this study are in accordance with research that has been carried out by several previous studies, namely by Anasi (2020); Hauret and Williams (2020); Hur (2020); Pawirosumarto et al. (2017) obtained results stating that the Work Environment has a positive effect on employee satisfaction. Based on the results of the description analysis, it can be seen that the work environment as measured by indicators of relationships with supervisors, benefits, contact with colleagues and workplace facilities for relationships with superiors are determinants of the work environment. This is a determinant for the employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food, so that cooperation must be established between superiors and subordinates so that SOPs are adhered to, so that service, quality and cleanliness of the PT Rekso Nasional Food environment are guaranteed. In addition, the work environment is also in accordance with the needs of employees, namely there is good cooperation between superiors and subordinates in carrying out work, there is good communication with fellow colleagues in the office and in the field, there are good work equipment and functions to support the implementation of tasks, there are service places for employees such as places of worship and toilets that are good and clean, there are good and comfortable working room conditions. This is what makes the work environment have the most significant influence on the job satisfaction of employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food.

The Effect Of Compensation On Employee Loyalty

In the results of the third hypothesis test (H3) it was found that compensation did not have a positive effect on the loyalty of employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food in Indonesia, and there was no positive relationship and significant influence on the loyalty of employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food. This means that compensation carried out at PT Rekso Nasional Food cannot have an effect on increasing employee loyalty. Based on the results of this study, it shows that hypothesis 3 is rejected, so the results of this study are not in line with the research conducted by Budiyo et al. (2022); Samat et al. (2020); Wulandari et al. (2021); Zufri et al., (2022); Idowu et al. (2019). He indicates in his study that pay has a favorable impact on employee loyalty. Employee loyalty at PT Rekso Nasional Food may not be affected by remuneration because of other variables, such as a work environment with high standards and stringent SOPs that encourage loyalty from workers. This is due to the diversity of options. The first is that, in general, workers believe that receiving money is expected of them, making the relationship between compensation and job loyalty irrelevant. The two workers with just a high school diploma believe that the salary is mostly utilized to cover everyday expenses and is thus unrelated to employee loyalty. This research is in line with the research conducted by Guchait et al. (2019), which explains that compensation has no effect on loyalty and compensation does not increase employee loyalty.

The Effect of the Work Environment on Employee Loyalty

In the results of the fourth hypothesis test (H4), it was found that The Work Environment

has a positive effect on the loyalty of PT Rekso Nasional Food employees in Indonesia, and there is a positive relationship and a significant influence on the loyalty of PT Rekso Nasional Food employees. This means that a good work environment at PT Rekso Nasional Food can have an influence on increasing employee loyalty. Based on the results of this study shows that hypothesis 4 is accepted, so the results of this study are not in line with the research conducted by Aboobaker et al. (2021); Ramadhanty et al. (2020); Samat et al. (2020); Susita et al. (2020); Zufri et al. (2022) where the results of the study show that the work environment has a positive effect on employee loyalty.

The Effect of Satisfaction on Employee Loyalty

According to the findings of the fifth hypothesis test (H5), employee satisfaction did not significantly and positively affect the loyalty of PT Rekso Nasional Food workers in Indonesia or have a good impact on the quality of those employees. This indicates that improving employee quality cannot be influenced by PT Rekso Nasional Food's happiness with its workforce. Based on the results of this study, it shows that hypothesis 5 is rejected, so the results of this study are not in line with the research carried out by (Mohd Said et al., 2020; Phuong and Vinh, 2020; Veloso et al., 2021) who showed the results of their research that employee satisfaction negatively affects employee loyalty. In this study, it was explained that the loyalty of PT Rekso Nasional Food employees was not influenced by employee satisfaction, this was due to the large number of employees with SMA-SMK Education whose satisfaction orientation was to get a salary. In addition, the work loyalty of employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food in terms of the length of time they worked in the company is relatively low. This is because employees do not intend to spend the rest of their careers in the company, and have the desire to find work elsewhere, and do not feel heavy to change jobs. The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Thanos et al. (2015) which explains that satisfaction negatively affects employee loyalty.

Effect Of Satisfaction Mediation On Compensation And Work Environment Relationships On Employee Loyalty

In the results of the sixth hypothesis test (H6) it was found that Job Satisfaction was not able to mediate a positive relationship of Compensation to employee loyalty of PT Rekso Nasional Food in Indonesia. This means job satisfaction is not a mediating factor between compensation and loyalty. Based on the results of this study, it shows that hypothesis 6 was rejected, so that the result of this study is not in line with the research conducted by Oleh Lestari et al. (2021) which shows the results of his research that employee satisfaction is able to mediate the positive influence of compensation on employee loyalty.

In the results of the aiming hypothesis test (H7) it was found that Job Satisfaction has a positive effect on the loyalty of employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food in Indonesia, and there is a positive relationship and a significant influence on the loyalty of employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food. This means that a good work environment at PT Rekso Nasional Food can have an influence on increasing employee loyalty. Based on the results of this study, it shows that hypothesis 7 is rejected, so that the results of this study are not in line with the research conducted by (Susita et al., 2020) showing the results of his research that employee satisfaction is able to mediate the positive influence of the work environment on employee loyalty.

CONCLUSION

The results of direct relationship research prove that compensation and the work environment have a positive effect on job satisfaction. Meanwhile, compensation does not have a positive effect on loyalty. The work environment positively affects the loyalty of employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food. Employee satisfaction is not able to mediate the positive influence of the work environment on the loyalty of Employees of PT Rekso Nasional Food.

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